

STRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT AND MOISTURE ABSORPTION BEHAVIOR OF A GRAPHITE/EPOXY OPTICAL METERING STRUCTURE FOR LANDSAT-D

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Specific details concerning the structural design, fabrication, and testing of the Thematic Mapper optical metering structure are presented. Design requirements are illustrated and compared with results from structural vibration and thermal tests. The approach used in the design of this graphite/epoxy and Invar structure is examined in detail to illustrate the desirability of this material combination in meeting design requirements. Test data are presented that characterize the absorbed moisture induced strain in the Gr/E laminates incorporated in the optical metering structure.

INTRODUCTION

The structural development of a graphite/epoxy (Gr/E) optical metering structure for the Thematic Mapper (TM) is presented in this paper. The TM, shown in Fig. 1, is the next generation of Multispectral Scanning radiometers. It is scheduled to be launched on a Delta aboard the new LANDSAT. D.

Figure 1. Thematic Mapper Scanner

spacecraft being managed by the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center. Fig. 2 shows the LANDSAT-D spacecraft. Similar to its predecessor, the Multispectral Scanner (MSS), which flew on the highly successful Earth Resources Technology Satellite (ERTS), the TM is a scanning radiometer that operates in both the visible and infrared spectral regimes. Major performance improvements of the TM in comparison to the MSS include geometric resolutions 2.5 times better, the addition of a sixth and seventh spectral band, and finer spectral resolution of each band. The optical metering structure (OMS) is critical to performance of the TM. Because of temperature variations in the TM's orbital and duty cycle, the OMS must be thermally stable across its operating range. In effect, the OMS had to be

Figure 2. LANDSAT-D Spacecraft

built of material that would have a near-zero thermal expansion coefficient over that range. Graphite/epoxy GY-70/X-30 was characterized as the best candidate material. The in-plane expansion coefficient of GY-70/X-30 quasi-isotropic laminate is less than $1.8 \times 10^{-7}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. Other advantages are the material's low density, excellent stiffness-to-weight and strength-to-weight ratios, and nonmagnetic properties.

Having had considerable experience in the design and fabrication of thermally stable structures and in the use of GY-70/X-30, General Dynamics was selected by Santa Barbara Research Center (SBRC) to develop the OMS. The prime contractor for the TM is the Hughes Aircraft Company (HAC), under contract to the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center. The radiometer portion of the TM is being designed and fabricated by SBRC, a HAC subsidiary.

DESCRIPTION

The optical metering structure as presented in this paper consists primarily of the graphite/epoxy and Invar components that serve as a metering structure or support for optical mirrors, detectors, and electronics. This structure consists of the following components (see Fig. 3).

1. Telescope housing and support cone
2. Radiation cooler adapter
3. Aft optics assembly made up of:
 - a. Aft optics plate
 - b. Relay optics base
 - c. Mirror mount
 - d. Relay optics housing

Each component has distinct functional and/or dimensional requirements. As an assembly, the hardware bolts and pins together satisfy overall dynamic and thermal stability performance requirements. Three complete OMS assemblies have thus far been fabricated and delivered to SBRC.

Figure 3. Graphite/Epoxy and Invar Hardware for the OMS

Telescope Housing

This housing is the largest and most optically critical component of the OMS. It supports the total OMS assembly from its outer support cone. The only aluminum (2024-T851) and high-strength-type graphite/epoxy (T300/934) in the entire structure is in this support cone. (T300/934 was used in this instance because strength and mounting interface considerations were of greater importance than thermal stability and stiffness.) The rest of the structure is high-modulus GY-70/X-30 graphite/epoxy and/or low-expansion Invar LR-35. The straight cylinder portion of the telescope housing is approximately 46 cm in diameter and 94 cm long. This cylinder has internal provisions for mounting the secondary mirror support spider (see Figs. 1 and 3), the primary mirror, and aft optics plate. The aft flange is used to mount the radiation cooler adapter.

GY-70/X-30 in a pseudoisotropic $[0/45/90/135]_8$ layup makes up the thermally stable and dynamically stiff metering structure that spans the 53 cm between secondary and primary mirror Invar interface mounts. Three-point support mounting is provided at both mirrors.

Several important functional requirements dictated the design of the primary mirror support.

- Limit radial load acting on mirror.
- Provide axial, lateral, and torsional stiffness.
- Accurately register and support a bonded-in 7.7-kg mirror.
- Provide for removability of mirror.
- Limit axial distortion effect.

These goals were met with three, two-piece, Invar mount pads that were bolted and bonded into the telescope housing.

Special bonding techniques and tooling were used to accurately and adequately bond all these Invar LR-35 parts in place. An epoxy adhesive (Hysol 934) was used to satisfy bond requirements, although lockbolts were employed to supplement the bond to avoid NDT type of inspection of these bond joints. In essence, the fastener guaranteed bond integrity should incomplete bonds occur. The bond also guaranteed permanent registration of the parts.

Eight light baffles were required inside the telescope cylinder. These annular, blade-like baffles were edge bonded to the cylinder inner skin using Hysol 934 adhesive. The baffles were equally spaced down the cylinder. The forward and aft ring, which attached to the secondary mirror support spider, served as the first and third baffle down the cylinder. The last baffle was located just in front of the primary mirror to perfectly define the light aperture. This baffle was precision machined to within 0.1 mm of its desired diameter and was concentric with the optical axis with 0.025 mm TIR. The machined inside edges of all these baffles were pressed epoxy fiberglass 0.20 mm thick bonded using Hysol 934 adhesive. The practicality of this design was verified when various repairs were successfully made to the required thin edge of the baffle.

Radiation Cooler Adapter

The radiation cooler adapter (RCA), which is made entirely of pseudoisotropic GY-70/X-30 except for the Invar LR-35 interface ring at either end, serves to mount the radiation cooler to the telescope housing at a 65° angle relative to the optical axis. Weight and stiffness dictated the design shown in Fig. 3. Because registration was essential in locating the RCA relative to the optical axis, stringent tolerance had to be met at initial calibration of the instrument and maintained through space operation. Thermal stability again was important. The elbow shape was obtained by cutting a 46-cm diameter cylinder at 12.5° , turning it 180° , and splicing it with a graphite/epoxy splice (T-section) ring. The various cable access holes were reinforced with bonded graphite/epoxy doublers of the same fiber orientation.

Aft Optics Assembly

The aft optics support plate, which is the only all-Invar component in the OMS, is multifunctional, as seen in Fig. 1.

- It supports the relay optics inside the telescope and RCA.
- It supports the central light baffle inside the telescope.
- Mounted to it are various detectors, a scan line corrector, shutters, transformers, and numerous other electrical and optical components.

The relay optics housing and base and the spherical mirror mount were the most complex hardware components to design. Loads, stiffness, and interface and functional requirements dictated the structural geometry shown in Fig. 3.

Since accessibility (interface) aspects were an essential part of the design requirements, it became necessary to use a fair amount of Invar in the make-and-break joints. Here again, the low expansion flanges and simple pin and fastener registration capability of the Invar proved advantageous.

The relay base structure contains an elliptical graphite/epoxy diaphragm that provides lateral support for the spherical mirror mount. The diaphragm was sized with specific stiffness limitations to make it compatible with inchworm adjuster load limitations. These adjusters attach to the three ears on the spherical mirror mount shown in Fig. 3. Tangent bars inside the spherical mirror mount limit mirror distortion caused by thermal and dynamic disturbances.

The relay optics housing both fastens and pins to the base and contains provision for the inchworms to attach. The three holes in the larger bottom flange allow the inchworms to pass through and attach to the spherical mirror mount. The smaller end of this graphite/epoxy cone-like structure supports the relay flat mirror. Inside the relay optics housing is an arrangement of light baffles also made from graphite/epoxy with pressed fiberglass edges.

The final weight measured for the first OMS produced (the engineering model) was approximately 1 kg over specification requirements, as depicted in Table 1. Tolerance control on Invar parts (especially the all-Invar aft optics plate) caused this overweight. Although weight requirements could have been satisfied by additional machining of specific Invar parts for this test unit, cost and schedule considerations were prohibitive. The second and third OMS units weighed 32.87 and 32.76 kg.

PART	CALC WT (kg)	ACTUAL WT (kg)
TELESCOPE HOUSING	18.78	18.55
RAD COOLING ADAPTER	4.75	4.63
AFT OPTICS PLATE	4.88	6.32
RELAY OPTICS HOUSING	2.11	2.22
RELAY OPTICS BASE	1.42	1.41
SPHERICAL MIRROR MOUNT	0.35	0.28
TOTAL	32.29	33.41

Table 1. Weight Summary for the OMS (First Unit)

FABRICATION

Unique to the fabrication of the various graphite/epoxy components is that all molded parts were made on aluminum male production molds (PDMO) (Figs. 4, 5, and 6). Layup techniques developed by General Dynamics and used in conjunction with precision-designed aluminum male PDMOs have proven most economical for this OMS hardware. High-quality seamless parts were produced with no scraggage because of wrinkles or fitup. Figure 7 illustrates some of the graphite/epoxy detail parts that make up the optical metering structure. Because of the many machined Invar and graphite/epoxy rings that interface with these molded parts, there was some concern that fitup problems would occur during assembly bonding. Instead, bondlines of 0.12 mm to 0.58 mm were held on as-built parts. Precision molding is made possible by this fabrication approach. One example is the radiation cooler adapter, which has a graphite/epoxy transition ring that is joined on each side by a cylinder section. Another example is the relay optics housing, which involves molding complex contours.

Figure 4. Production Mold for Telescope Housing and RCA Shown with Completed Tube

Figure 5. Production Molds for Support Cones (Silicone Overpress in Place), RCA Transition Ring, and Other Small Cylinders

Figure 6. Production Mold for Relay Optics Housing

the telescope housing portion of the OMS. The actual expansion measurement recorded was between the secondary mirror mount interface and the aft optics support plate. The distance between the laser mirrors, which mount to these interfaces, was monitored by the built-in sensor of a Hewlett-Packard Model 5526A laser dilatometer. The telescope housing was suspended in a temperature-vacuum

Assembly-bonding of the OMS was accomplished in only three fixtures. Two small fixtures were used for assembly bonding of the spherical mirror mount assembly and the secondary mirror spider assembly.

The entire OMS was final-assembly-bonded together in the major assembly fixture shown in Fig. 8. The basic philosophy of having a common "do it all" fixture for bonding was to maintain the precision part-to-part relationship dictated by design requirements. Unfortunately, the necessary precision in parallelism and flatness could not be achieved at certain interfaces. Tolerance on the order of ± 0.03 mm proved beyond the capability of tool inspection techniques. Although this major assembly fixture was used to fit up and assembly-bond all components, additional machining was necessary to achieve the tolerances required. A central shaft representing the centerline of the telescope (relative to the primary and secondary mirror) was placed between centers on a hand lathe. Runouts on such critical surfaces as the primary mirror mounts (coplanar within 0.03 mm), the aft optics plate mounting ring (parallel within 0.03 mm), the RCA mounting flange (parallel within 0.13 mm), and the OMS support ring (parallel within 0.05 mm) were checked and then corrected in this setup.

THERMAL EXPANSION TEST

A simple thermal vacuum test, illustrated in Fig. 9, was employed to measure the actual expansion of

Figure 7. Molded and Flat Laminate Graphite/
Epoxy Details

Figure 8. Major Assembly
Bond Fixture for the OMS

chamber by means of vibration-isolating suspension. An aluminum ring was attached to the support cone to simulate the thermal expansion constraints of the OMS interface structure. Before testing, the telescope housing was subjected to ten stabilization cycles (20°C to 74°C to -15°C to 20°C). Actual test measurements were recorded as the telescope was cycled from -15°C to 68°C in four steps.

The average CTE over this range for the telescope housing in the axial direction was $-1.2 \times 10^{-7}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for this first OMS. The following two OMS housings were similarly tested and found to have CTE values of $0.83 \times 10^{-7}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $1.04 \times 10^{-7}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. All three housings were therefore within the desired $\pm 1.44 \times 10^{-7}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ range for overall CTE.

Figure 9. Thermal Expansion Test Setup

VIBRATION TESTS

The optical metering structure was assembled using aluminum dummy masses to simulate actual optical and electronic components. The unit was then instrumented with accelerometers and strain gages and mounted to a vibration fixture. The unit was subjected to low-level sine, low-level random, and qualification-level sine vibration in three orthogonal axes. Objectives of the test were to qualify the structure to the design acceleration levels, determine the dynamic response to low-level sine and random excitation, evaluate the structural damping characteristics, and provide experimental verification of analytically predicted resonant frequencies. The design sinusoidal acceleration level for each axis was 15g peak from 20 to 100 Hz input at the OMS cone mounting surface. The structure passed these tests with no failures. Strain gage data confirmed the low stress levels predicted by analysis. The OMS was designed to sustain a 40g quasistatic acceleration load in addition to the previously described sinusoidal acceleration load.

Low-level (0.25g peak) sine sweeps were made from 20 to 2000 Hz in each of the three axes. The measured resonant frequencies of the structure compared favorably with analytical predictions made with a detailed NASTRAN finite element analysis. A fundamental frequency of 160 Hz was observed. The structure is generally somewhat stiffer than predicted. The greater stiffness was expected because of the conservative approach taken in constructing the NASTRAN structural model.

MOISTURE ABSORPTION

The moisture absorbant characteristic of graphite/epoxy introduces the problem of dimensional change. Either moisture absorption or desorption will cause expansion or contraction of the optical metering structure (OMS) and result in a focusing problem with the instrument. For the TM telescope a period of two years can be anticipated from the start of fabrication of the OMS until launch into orbit. Performance of the telescope will be impaired if length change greater than 20×10^{-6} cm/cm occurs. An unprotected structure could expand more than 50×10^{-6} cm/cm in a laboratory environment with uncontrolled humidity exposure.

A method for effective moisture control for the TM was necessary. A moisture control plan was developed. It included four elements:

1. Temperature and humidity controls of the laboratory environment in which the TM telescope was assembled and tested.
2. A test and measurement program of GY-70/X-30 humidity absorption characteristics.
3. A method for monitoring the weight gain of the telescope structure during assembly and testing.
4. Analytical prediction of future moisture induced strains of the telescope structure.

Environment

The assembly and testing of the TM requires approximately a 14-month effort. The major portion of that time takes place in a class 10,000 clean laboratory, where the average temperature is held to 21°C and special dehumidifiers control the relative humidity to 30% during the day and less than 20% during non-working hours. A dewpoint hygrometer, a psychrometer and a 7-day temperature chart recorder are used simultaneously to continually monitor the laboratory environment.

Test and Measurement

An experimental test program was initiated to arrive at the following objectives:

1. Determine the desorption characteristics of GY-70/X-30 graphite/epoxy at high temperature by baking test samples of an 8-ply and a 16-ply composite material to its maximum dry state condition.
2. Conduct a moisture absorption test with the same material by exposure to 21°C and 75% relative humidity until saturation occurs. Arrive at a diffusion coefficient D_x and expansion coefficient β for the above test condition.

High Temperature Bakeout

A total of 32 test coupons were used. The material came from the same laminates from which the TM engineering model and protoflight optical metering structures were fabricated. The test samples as shown in Table 2 were selected to include different laminate thicknesses and paint conditions representative of the TM OMS. The test samples were baked out at 49°C, 55°C, and 66°C until they had reached the maximum dry state after 3,000 hours, thus providing a good "zero" starting point for the humidity absorption test (Fig. 10). A precise measurement system had to be employed to make

GROUP	QUANTITY	MATERIAL ORIGIN	ONE SIDE PAINTED	THICKNESS (cm)
A	5	PROTOFLIGHT	X	0.20
B	5	PROTOFLIGHT		0.20
C	5	PROTOFLIGHT	X	0.10
D	5	PROTOFLIGHT		0.10
E	12	ENGINEERING MODEL		0.10

Table 2. Definition of Humidity Absorption Test Samples

Figure 10. Percent Weight Loss versus Time^{1/2} for Three Different Bakeout Temperatures

weight measurements in the 10⁻⁶ gram range and dilation measurements in the 2 × 10⁻⁶ cm range. A standard semi-microbalance is used to measure the weight, but for change in lengths a dilatometer had to be designed and fabricated (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. Dilatometer and Microbalance

The dilatometer system consists of a Kaman sensor unit mounted in an Invar head, an oscillator-demodulator unit, and a combination power supply and digital readout. The sensor operates on the eddy current principle that requires a nonmagnetic target be attached to the test specimen. The sensor does not make contact with the target. Its close proximity creates a specific eddy current field which causes oscillations at a particular frequency. This frequency is then demodulated into a dc output which is read on the digital voltmeter. The system was calibrated to read 1 mv for 10⁻⁶ cm/cm of material expansion. Three quartz standards were used as reference checks for weight and length measures. Before

and after each batch of test specimens was measured, each quartz standard was also measured and compared with its previous reading. Any significant deviation was investigated. One of the three standards was kept with the test samples in the humidity chamber, so that unforeseen shifts in the epoxy compound that bonds the aluminum targets to the test specimen can be detected when the standard is measured.

It was planned from the outset to make both weight and length measurements at the time of the bakeout, but due to the unavailability of the dilatometer only the weight of the 32 samples was measured. Consequently, strain readings were not possible and the expansion coefficient β could not be determined. By the time the test samples were ready for the humidity absorption test, the dilatometer was ready and used for all subsequent measurements.

Humidity Absorption Test

The main objective of the test is to determine a credible diffusion coefficient for a 21°C, 75% relative humidity environment. Analysis of GY-70/X-30 composite material previously performed by D. F. Adams for SBRC [Ref. 1] had assumed diffusion coefficients of 2.6×10^{-10} cm²/sec and 5.2×10^{-10} cm²/sec for calculating future moisture induced dimensional growth of the TM protoflight model. These values varied considerably with published reports by General Dynamics-Convaair, the hardware manufacturer [Ref. 2]. Because of these uncertainties as to an exact value for a diffusion coefficient, the humidity absorption test program was initiated. Every effort was made to exercise maximum control over the test samples, the test condition and the data analysis.

The humidity test was conducted using the 32 test samples that had been dried out and had attained a near zero moisture content. The weight and dilation measurements were computer processed and the average of all the curves is shown in Figs. 12 and 13. The expansion coefficient β is shown in Fig. 13 as the slope of the curve of the average 32 samples. Note the curves are exceptionally linear and practically identical for each size of specimen. Although over 9,000 hours have

Figure 12. Percent Weight Gain versus Time^{1/2} for 0.1-cm and 0.2-cm GY-70/X-30 Gr/E Laminate Samples

Figure 13. Strain versus Percent Weight Gain (Nonequilibrium Values) for 0.1-cm and 0.2-cm GY-70/X-30 Laminate Samples

passed, the test is still in progress. The curves are still linear and have not reached their exponential rolloff point. Consequently, an exact diffusion coefficient could not yet be calculated.

Monitoring the OMS for Dimensional Changes

Structural changes of the optical metering structure on the order of 2×10^{-6} cm/cm are extremely difficult to measure with accuracy and repeatability. A practical approach is the use of witness pieces that are easily measured and are a good indicator of the state of the hardware. The witness pieces are produced from the same laminates as the OMS. Ten pieces are used with every OMS. Their weight is recorded from the very beginning of their life cycle with the designated OMS. The witness pieces are never separated from the OMS so that the environmental exposure remains the same at all times. Change of weight data are converted to strain values, by using the strain versus percent weight gain curves derived from the humidity absorption test. Fig. 14 shows a plot of strain versus time for an average of ten witness pieces indicating the strain level of the flight model OMS.

Analytical Predictions

It was recognized early in the TM program that moisture induced strains in the optical metering structure must be predicted reliably if planning of future

Figure 14. Average Strain versus Time for S/N 3 (Flight Model) OMS Witness Samples

environmental exposures are to include adequate protection against overexposure to humidity. Dr. D. F. Adams, University of Wyoming, was the principle contributor to the solution of the problem. A data base, Table 3, of time and humidity exposure was computer modeled to produce a projected graphical strain history of the TM (Fig. 15). The period marked "Santa Barbara Research Center Clean Room" is 371 days and ends in December 1980. The relative humidity of this cleanroom was measured approximately every 2 hours during the past 13 months. These data were used in the present analysis to project the humidity levels through December 1980. The coefficient of moisture expansion $\beta = 163 \times 10^{-6} / \%M$ used in the environmental exposure profile is derived from the experimental data collected and analyzed during the humidity experiment previously reported.

ACTIVITY	TIME (days)	RELATIVE HUMIDITY (%)	COMMENTS
STRUCTURE FABRICATION	156	--	VARIABLES FROM 5 TO 50%
BAKEOUT	5	0	VACUUM BAKE AT 66°C
TELESCOPE ASSEMBLY AND TEST	371	12-30	12 HRS EXPOSURE EACH LEVEL
VIBRATION TESTS	56	5	TM UNDER N ₂ PURGE
THERMAL VACUUM TEST	21	0	--
POST-THERMAL VACUUM TESTS	48	5	TM MOSTLY UNDER N ₂ PURGE
SPACECRAFT INTEGRATION	308	--	VARIABLES FROM 5 TO 50%
PRELAUNCH OPERATIONS	60	5	TM UNDER N ₂ PURGE
ORBIT	730	0	2 YEARS IN ORBIT

Table 3. SBRC Thematic Mapper Flight Model Full Life Environmental Exposure

Figure 15. Predicted Strain History of the Thematic Mapper Flight Model OMS

CONCLUSION

The OMS design presented here was an attempt at optimizing the use of Gr/E and Invar to meet performance requirements within schedule and cost constraints.

As a result of the combined analytical and experimental effort described above, the optical metering structure was shown to meet thermal and structural design requirements and was accepted for subsequent assembly into the Thematic Mapper for complete mechanical, electrical, and optical testing of this instrument.

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